

Halogenation. Part V. Bromination and Iodination of some Fatty Acids.

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Bromo derivatives of the fatty acids are generally obtained either by the direct action of bromine in presence of halogen carriers at high temperatures, sometimes under pressure, or by the replacement of hydroxyl group in the hydroxy derivatives of the fatty acids by the action of hydrobromic acid or phosphorus bromide. Iodo derivatives are obtained either by the action of phosphorus iodide on the hydroxy derivatives of the fatty acids or by the replacement of bromine in the bromo derivatives of the acids by means of iodine.

Attempts have been made in this paper to prepare the bromo and iodo derivatives of some of the fatty acids with the help of potassium bromide and sulphuric acid and iodine and sulphuric acid respectively. In the case of lower fatty acids poor yield of the halogen derivatives has been obtained, whereas in the case of higher fatty acids comparatively a much better yield of the α -bromo and α -iodo derivatives has been found. No appreciable difference in the yield of iodoacetic acid is noticeable when acetic acid or acetic anhydride is used for the purpose. A slightly better yield of the bromo and iodo derivatives is obtained with acetic acid or acetic anhydride when nitrosulphonic acid mixture (a mixture containing about 50% of fuming nitric acid and about 50% of nitrosulphonic acid, the latter obtained by passing a current of dry sulphur dioxide through nitric acid) is used in place of concentrated sulphuric acid. In other cases, there is no appreciable difference in the yield of the halogen derivatives, when concentrated sulphuric acid or nitrosulphonic acid mixture is employed. α -Bromo derivatives have been obtained from acetic acid, acetic anhydride, propionic acid, butyric anhydride, isobutyric acid, lauric acid, myristic acid, palmitic and stearic acids and α -iodo derivatives from acetic acid, acetic anhydride, propionic acid, butyric anhydride, isobutyric acid, palmitic and stearic acids.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The acid or the anhydride was taken in a flask provided with a reflux condenser, potassium bromide or iodine (as the case may be)

was added and the flask heated on a water-bath. Concentrated sulphuric acid or nitrosulphonic acid (as the case may be) was then added ($\frac{1}{2}$ c.c. at a time). Heating was continued for about 5 hours and then the mixture treated with sulphurous acid to remove any excess of bromine or iodine and then extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried with calcium chloride and ether evaporated off on a water-bath. If the residue left behind is solid, it is purified by crystallisation from water or alcohol. If the residue is liquid, it is distilled under reduced pressure. The results obtained with different acids or anhydrides are summarised in the following table.

Substance.	Amount taken.	Halogenating agent.	Product.
Acetic acid	20 c.c.	Potassium bromide (5g.) and nitrosulphonic acid mixture (10 c.c.)	Bromoacetic acid (1 g.), m.p. 49-50°
Acetic anhydride	"	"	"
Propionic acid	"	Potassium bromide (5g.) and conc. sulphuric acid (10 c.c.)	α -Bromopropionic acid (3 g.), b.p. 204-207°
Butyric anhydride	"	"	α -Bromobutyric acid (5 g.), b.p. 127°/25 mm.
<i>iso</i> Butyric acid	"	"	α -Bromo <i>iso</i> butyric acid (5 g.), m.p. 48°
*Lauric acid	5 g.	"	α -Bromolauric acid (2.5 g.), m.p. 31.5°
*Palmitic acid	"	"	α -Bromopalmitic acid (3 g.), m.p. 52°
*Stearic acid	"	"	α -Bromostearic acid (3 g.), m.p. 60°
Acetic acid	20 c.c.	Iodine (5 g.) and nitrosulphonic acid mixture (10 c.c.)	Iodoacetic acid (1 g.), m.p. 83°
Acetic anhydride	"	"	"
Propionic acid	"	"	α -Iodopropionic acid (1 g.), m.p. 45°
Butyric anhydride	"	"	α -Iodobutyric acid (4.5 g.), m.p. 41°
<i>iso</i> Butyric acid	"	"	α -Iodo <i>iso</i> butyric acid (4.5 g.), m.p. 73.5°
*Palmitic acid	5 g.	"	α -Iodopalmitic acid (2 g.), m.p. 57°
*Stearic acid	"	"	α -Iodostearic acid (2 g.), m.p. 66°

* Carbon tetrachloride (10 c.c.) used as solvent.